

A Study on Isolation and Identification of Candida Species from Various Clinical Samples in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract

Introduction: Candida is a yeast-like fungus that is a common human commensal. As the host's resistance to infection is reduced, either locally or systemically, they become pathogens and cause illnesses. The present study was conducted to isolate, identify and characterize Candida species from various clinical samples at VIMS, Ballari.

Materials and Methods: This prospective Study was conducted in the department of Microbiology, VIMS Ballary from October 2022 to April 2023. A total of 6781 clinical samples were examined. Gram stain, germ tube test, and inoculation on commercially available CHROM agar were performed for these isolates.

Results: Candida isolates were found in 186 of the 6781 clinical specimens. Majority of isolates were from urine (47%) followed by sputum (30%), vaginal swab (16%), blood (4%), and pus (3%). *Candida albicans* (42%) was the most isolated species followed by *C. tropicalis* (25%), *C. glabrata* (16%), *C. krusei* (13%), and *C. Parapsilosis* (4%).

Conclusions: *Candida albicans* was identified as a prevalent pathogenic yeast in our study. The capacity to identify inherently resistant organisms is aided by the ability to characterise *Candida* to the species level. CHROM agar is a rapid, easy, and low-cost method for identifying such species.

Keywords: Candida, Clinical Samples, Chrom Agar.

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Introduction

Yeast infections vary in severity, ranging from minor infections [1] to potentially fatal sepsis [2]. *Candida* is one of the most important yeast genera due to its significant morbidity and mortality. At least 15 *Candida* species have been linked to human illnesses [3]. The majority of *Candida* species are considered normal skin and mucous membrane residents. However, under certain

conditions, these microorganisms have the potential to express virulence factors that render them pathogenic or opportunistic, particularly when the patient is suffering from a debilitating clinical condition [4,5], or when invasive devices are used [6,7], or when immunosuppression is present.

The most severe cases of candidiasis are nosocomial, and the source of infection might

be endogenous or external [8]. *Candida albicans* is the most commonly reported species causing human illness [9], however additional species such as *C. glabrata*, *C. parapsilosis*, *C. tropicalis*, and *C. krusei* have also been recorded [10]. The number of yeast infections appears to have grown dramatically in recent decades [11,12]. While *Candida albicans* is still responsible for the majority of yeast infections, non-*albicans* species appear to be on the rise [13,14].

The biggest significance of these recent alterations in the prevalence and epidemiology of severe *Candida* infections resides in the inherent disparities in sensitivity to antifungal therapy between each of these species [15]. In many circumstances, identifying *Candida* species allows one to forecast their sensitivity to antifungal drugs. The purpose of this prospective study is to isolate, identify, and characterise *Candida* SPP from diverse clinical samples at VIMS, Ballari.

Materials and Methods

It is a prospective research conducted by the Microbiology department of VIMS Ballary between October 2022 and December 2023. All clinical samples suspected of fungal infection that were submitted to the microbiology laboratory throughout the research period were included.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Samples that include typical flora

2. Contamination of culture plate and multimicrobial development
3. Patients receiving antifungal therapy

All clinical samples were obtained according to clinical and laboratory protocols. [16] Gram's stain was conducted on direct samples that were put into Sabouraud dextrose agar and incubated for 24 hours at 37 degrees Celsius. The positives were identified as either *Candida albicans* or *Candida dubliniensis* based on a germ tube test. *C. albicans* was further recognised by its growth at 45°C and the production of chlamydospores on agar containing cornmeal. All of the isolates were submitted to a sugar assimilation test for species verification. *Candida* spp. were simultaneously inoculated on CHROM agar (Hi-media, India) and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Species were identified based on the type and colour of colonies on CHROM agar medium, following manufacturer's instructions.

Results

In the present study, a total of 6781 various specimens were collected, out of which 186 *Candida* isolates were obtained. More isolates were obtained from Males than females and among the age group 31-40 years.

The highest number of isolates were obtained from urine (47%) followed by sputum (30%), vaginal swab (16%), blood (4%), and pus (3%). (Table 1)

Table 1: Type of samples

Specimen	Number of isolates	Percentage (%)
Urine	87	47
Blood	8	4
Vaginal Swab	30	16
Sputum	55	30
Pus	6	3
Total	186	100

Figure 1: Type of samples

Candida albicans (42%) was the most isolated species followed by *C. tropicalis* (25%), *C. grablata* (16%), *C.krusei* (13%), and *C. Parapsilosis* (4%). (Table 2)

Table 2: The distribution of different Candida species

Candida species	Number of isolates	Percentage (%)
<i>C.tropicalis</i>	47	25
<i>C.grablata</i>	29	16
<i>C.albicans</i>	79	42
<i>C.krusei</i>	24	13
<i>C.parapsilosis</i>	7	4
Total	186	100

Figure 2: Distribution of Candida Species

Discussion

The percentage of *C. albicans* isolation in this investigation was 42%. According to Manjunath *et al.*[18] and Fasow *et al.*[17], *C. albicans* is the most common (51%) isolate. In this investigation, the highest percentage of Candida species were found in the samples of urine (47%), sputum (30%), vaginal swabs (16%), blood (4%) and pus (3%). According to Arasi's [19] study, the majority of candida species were found in urine (41.6%), sputum (20.4%), high vaginal swabs (14%) and pus (6%). Alvarez-Lerma *et al.* [20], Sankarankutty Jay and Vipparthi Harita [21] found that more strains were identified from urine.

Chromogenic agar, which contains enzyme substrates coupled to chromogenic substances, is a more recent and quick way to speciate Candida. The chromogenic compounds emit colour when a certain enzyme breaks down the substrate. Certain yeasts can be presumed to be identified based on colour change caused by the activity of several enzymes generated by yeast species [22].

Conclusion

Characterizing Candida to the species level enables the identification of the intrinsically resistant species. CHROM agar is a simple, affordable, and quick technique for identifying these species.

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